

CURRENT ASPECTS OF INTRODUCING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE MODERN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: Today, the share of independent education in the world's top 1000 universities is at least over 50%. In this regard, the issues of transformation in the introduction of independent education in the higher education system of our republic, effective experiences of the most advanced TOP-1000 universities in the introduction of independent education, the higher education system facing the introduction of independent education in the process of transformation problems and prospects for their solution are discussed.

Key words: independent learning (IL), independent work (IW), concept, independent work under the guidance of the teacher, independent work without the participation of the teacher, IW in the classroom, IW outside the classroom, working in small groups IW in the form of project work, normative documents on providing IL, scientific and methodical materials on IL, working with educational literature in IL, working with electronic educational literature and database in IL.

Adoption of the Law "On Education" in a new version, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019, in the process of accelerating reforms in the field of education in the new era of development of our country. The concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", and the priorities of the systematic reform of higher education approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 dated October 8, 2019, higher education with modern knowledge and independent thinking raising the process of training of qualified personnel to a new level in terms of quality, modernization of higher education and development of the social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies are given special importance as strategic issues.

In particular, in the Concept "increasing the share of independent education hours, students' independent education, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, formation of entrepreneurial skills, introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process, educational "to direct the educational process to the formation of practical skills, in this regard, to widely introduce advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and teaching-methodical materials into the educational process based on

international educational standards." It is also emphasized that students can acquire the necessary competences of specialists through independent education, independent work, continuous improvement of their skills, development of creative creativity, research, and logical thinking. The organization of the educational process plays an important role in the training of specialist personnel. Currently, the ratio of classroom (contact) and independent education in the curricula of students is from 40/60 percent ratio to 50/50 percent ratio in undergraduate education, from 30/70 percent ratio to 50/50 percent ratio in master's specialties. allocated to the percentage ratio. In the process of changing the educational program, a number of issues and problems of sciences should be studied through independent education. Independent education is the independent acquisition by students of a part of the program materials in one or another subject.

One of the main tasks of higher education is to direct a specialist to self-development, to increase his knowledge independently, to form a creative personality capable of innovative activities. The only thing lacking is the teacher's giving the student ready knowledge for the implementation of such a task. Such a way turns the student into a passive consumer of learning. However, today we need not a passive consumer of knowledge, but an active creator of it. The result should be such that the future specialist can express any theoretical and practical problem, find the most suitable and appropriate results, able to scientifically or methodically analyze the ways to solve it, and prove its correctness. let it be Changes in the education system are closely related to the content of education.

Updates also require thinking about new forms and methods of organizing student studies. In this sense, the organization of students' independent work is not only an important form, but also an important part of the educational process. All of this envisages the acquisition of modern methods of teaching (receiving), the development of students' creative abilities, taking into account the opportunities and potential of each student, and the transition from group studies to individual studies. It is necessary to organize this process in such a way that, as a result, the ability, skills and qualifications of the student to learn independently and apply this knowledge to life are formed.

What should be the goals and tasks of organizing students' independent work: the main goal of students' independent work is the formation and development of knowledge, skills and abilities that are necessary for independent performance of educational work. The tasks of students' independent work may include the following: a) determining the necessary measures to search for new information to perform independent work; b) use of information sources in the process of independent work; c) work with regulatory documents, scientific and methodical materials, educational literature; g) working with electronic educational literature and

databases; d) preparing work plans for examination, processing them according to the expert's opinion, creating conditions for systematic and creative execution of work; e) explaining and defending the developed solution, idea or project.

Organizational forms, options for independent work, and tasks for independent completion of all subjects are developed in the department according to the time limit set for the independent work of students. Organizing students' independent work means expressing the goals and tasks of each, developing guidelines or methodical recommendations, and selecting scientific literature in order to compile a list of themes and forms of its methodical support.

Independent education, on the one hand, is a systematic activity aimed at forming theoretical knowledge, practical skills and competencies based on independent mastering of educational material, tasks of different levels of complexity, creative and independent performance of practical tasks in the audience and outside the audience. Independent education, on the other hand, is a form of education aimed at strengthening the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities, and independent study of additional information or material.

Independent work is an active method of education that solves the educational task under the teacher's assignment and guidance, and independent work is the organization and implementation of specific activities of students in connection with the set goal. Student's independent work is his activity based on high level of activity, creativity, independent analysis, initiative and timely and perfect performance of all tasks. So to speak, all activities aimed at educating the future specialist's way of thinking form their basis. Any type of training that allows the student to develop independent thinking and increase his cognitive activity is closely related to independent work.

Independent education should not be understood as leaving students to their own devices and reducing the tasks and workloads given to them, but it is an interactive independent activity of students regularly guided by teachers. The role of independent education in improving the quality of the educational process is great. Realizing this, the share of independent study hours allocated to educational activities in higher educational institutions of our country is regularly increased. The student should understand that independent education is carried out in his interest. In fact, the concept of a student's independent work means a set of independent work that is carried out in the classroom and outside it, under the guidance of a teacher or without the participation of a teacher.

In the study of any subject, three interrelated forms of TMI organization are noticeable: 1. Independent works outside the auditorium. 2. Independent works in the Auditorium. It is organized directly under the guidance of the teacher. 3. Creative work. Creative form can be extremely diverse. Including: analytical data, lectures and

written works on the given subject related to separate chapters of the subject being studied. It is appropriate to give the student the right to choose the topic, even the leader; preparation of illustrative materials on the chosen subject, in which the topic is given by the teacher, its content and form, execution is determined by the student; creating scientific crosswords whose size, complexity, and content are formed by the student himself; to write a review of a scientific monograph of a modern scientist, a writer's work, with a personal evaluation and a recommendation for its use, separating the main ideas and rules; perform various types of homework.

This includes solving exercises and problems, translating or retelling the text, choosing and studying literary or scientific sources, making various tables, performing graphic work, performing various calculations, etc. includes; performing individual tasks aimed at developing initiative and independence in the student. Individual assignments can be received by each student or a group of students; completion of course work, graduation qualification work; scientific-theoretical or scientific-practical conferences, examinations, preparations for Olympiads; write a scientific essay on the chosen topic. In order to form and develop a positive attitude to TMI, at each stage, the specific goals and tasks of the work should be explained, and students' understanding of these goals and tasks should be controlled. These works will be the basis for the formation of the skills and abilities of the student to independently set tasks and choose goals.

The "Instructions on organization and control of independent education of students in the credit-module system in higher education institutions" serves as a guideline for organizing independent education of students. Scientific aspects of organizing independent education of students, theoretical and practical bases of independent work have been developed in the instruction, the processes necessary for independent work of students have been researched. The main forms and types of independent education of students are described in detail, and the methods of independent work that they can perform both in theoretical and practical lesson processes are shown. In order to attract students to independent work, methodical recommendations are given, which, in turn, is a guide for those engaged in independent education.

This instruction is based on the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 824 of December 31, 2020 "On measures to improve the system related to the organization of the educational process in higher education institutions" and the Higher and o It was developed on the basis of the order of the Minister of Special Education No. 311 of July 16, 2021 "On approval of state educational standards of higher education".

The Instruction on the establishment of SIL is based on the following general rules: 1.1. The student's independent educational workload is an integral part of the

educational work specified in the curriculum for mastering a particular subject. 1.2. The independent education of the student is carried out in the form of independent work under the direct supervision of the teacher or independent study of topics in the subject (module) in the auditorium and outside the auditorium (without taking into account the hours of the auditorium allocated in the curriculum). means a set of educational works. 1.3. Independent education is a systematic activity aimed at forming theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications based on independent mastering of educational material, assignments of different levels of complexity, creative and independent performance of practical tasks in the audience and outside the audience.

Independent work is an active method of education that solves the educational task under the teacher's instructions and guidance. Independent work is the organization and implementation of specific activities of students in connection with the set goal. Student's independent work is his activity based on high level of activity, creativity, independent analysis, initiative and timely and perfect performance of all tasks. 1.4. The type and form of independent work is determined based on the characteristics of a specific educational field (specialty) and subject (module).

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